

Cover to cover: A thesis radio journey

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I have been researching third space practitioners and the factors that impact their efficacy in Australian higher education since 2016 for my PhD. As this journey comes to an end, “listen” as I take you between the covers of my thesis and explore key ideas and findings, interspersed with some of my favourite musical cover versions. This one-hour show was initially “broadcast” as part of ALTC radio at the 2024 ALT conference in the UK. I used cover versions because scholarship is largely about building on what has come before and adding your own spin.

Engage

[Music plays] You are listening to ALTC Radio. I'm Colin Simpson, and the program is Cover to Cover. We just heard from Messerschups with their version of Wicked Game originally recorded by Chris Isaak a little while ago.

In the next hour, I'm going to share some of my favourite cover versions and also take you between the covers of my work in progress doctoral thesis. (It's getting close. It's getting close). I kind of like the analogy of the cover version to describe academic research. It's all about building on work that's come before but putting your own spin on things to hopefully create something new. I should probably tell you a little bit about myself before we get under the covers, so to speak.

I have worked in the tertiary education third space since 2003, both in vocational education and training and also higher education. Third space workers in tertiary education occupy roles which are neither academic nor entirely professional. They kind of transcend or cross or sit in between those barriers. And so, we're talking about things like learning design, educational technology, academic development, that kind of stuff. So, I've worked at the Canberra Institute of Technology, Australian National University, Monash University, Swinburne University, and I'm currently a senior learning designer at the University of Sydney.

I am also one of the leaders of the ASCILITE TELedvisors Network, and we're a community of practitioners for people working in the tertiary education third space, we have been operating since 2017. We do webinars, have a fairly active discussion board and do what we can to support people in these kinds of roles.

Anyway, enough about me. Let's have another song. [Music plays] And that was the lovely Mary Jo Starr AKA Kaarin Fairfax, with her interpretation of the Hunters and Collectors classic 'Throw your arms around me'. You will not find that on Spotify. That was on a very small release called Used and Recovered by. It was a 3RRR Community Radio compilation.

Given the number of times that I've already mentioned the third space, you may not be surprised to hear that this is the subject of my PhD research. I've been doing this part-time at the University

of Sydney since 2016. Firstly, under Peter Goodyear and now under Lina Markauskaite. I first had the urge to do this after I started working in higher education in 2015 and realised that things were quite different for third space professional staff in higher ed than I'd sort of been experiencing in the vocational education sector. I was finding it a lot harder to get things done, and I kind of wanted to know why. So, as I explored the literature and went down a range of rabbit holes, I realised that a lot of what I was reading didn't really mesh with my own experiences.

There's some very good literature about the third space, but a lot of it just was incomplete. My first challenge was I wanted to talk about three roles collectively, so learning designers, educational technologists, and academic developers. And this was just not a term that existed in parallel to this. Some colleagues and I created the TELedvisors network, the community of practice that I mentioned before, and we coined the term edvisor, which I've kind of revised to EdAdvisor because people kept getting edvisor wrong, which is a portmanteau of educator and advisor. And I've landed on these four research questions.

1. Who are EdAdvisor in Australian higher education and what do they do?
2. How do our EdAdvisor contribute to better learning and teaching?
3. What are the enablers and inhibitors of EdAdvisor practices?
4. What actions can be taken to enhance EdAdvisor efficacy?

I'm not entirely sold on the wording of these questions, but it's pretty close. I think that will get me there.

Let's have another track. [Music plays] Right there we had The Slits, their interpretation of 'I heard it through the grapevine'.

So, let's continue with my little story about my doctoral research. I'm taking an abductive approach epistemologically, if you want to put it that way. Because this lets me be informed by theory but means that I'm not necessarily beholden to it.

I'm still able to see where the findings take me in terms of my theoretical frameworks. There are two you've probably guessed Third Space Theory is definitely one of those. There's different flavours of Third Space Theory. But obviously I'm looking at third space as it applies to higher education, which was largely popularised by Celia Whitchurch in the late two thousands, drawing on sociolinguistic theory from Homi Bhabha.

Whitchurch's work focuses on boundaries between academic and professional or administrative staff, and she puts people into one of four categories: bounded professionals, cross boundary professionals, unbounded professionals or blended professionals. The second theoretical lens that I'm using is practice theory and if there are, you know, a handful of flavours of Third Space Theory, there are a million versions of practice theory. I would kind of sum it up though, as "I do, therefore, I am". Now practice theory broadly is concerned with what we do and what that tells us about ourselves. The application that I'm most interested in is work done by Stephen Kemmis in, I guess, the 2010s who sort of breaks practice down into "doings", which is, well, the things that you're doing, "sayings", which is largely the understanding of why you might be doing something and "relatings", which are the interactions between the people involved in doings. Kemmis adds this idea of practice architectures, which are really important in the third space EdAdvisor world because that essentially involves creating the conditions for someone else's practice to occur.

So, using all of these elements, I'm basically exploring what it is that EdAdvisors are doing and the different areas of higher education that impact that.

Let's have another track. [Music plays]

Iggy pop there with his take on Johnny O'Keefe's. Australian rock and roll classic, Real wild child (Wild One).

So, when I'm talking about EdAdvisors. I am talking about people in three roles. Let me give you a very potted rundown on what I think are the distinguishing features of these. So academic developers are more likely to be people in academic positions, generally women obviously, you know, your mileage may vary. Some of the primary activities that academic developers are involved in are building capability, quality management of teaching – so, teaching evaluations, providing feedback peer review of teaching – and designing teaching and learning, which is kind of something that they do share with learning designers.

And this is probably more the curriculum side of design rather than the designing learning activities and resources. They'd also be involved in nurturing learning and teaching culture and research. This is probably one of the more distinguishing characteristics of academic developers largely because they get to hold academic roles.

The academic status of the academic developer is really important. It allows academics to feel that they're working with someone who actually understands their practices, their challenges, what they're going through, and most academic developers have reported that this just makes life a lot easier.

Moving on to educational technologists, you may also know them as learning technologists. People in this role are more likely to be male, which is against the norm for particularly people in professional staff positions in higher education. On a side note, I recognise that I'm talking to people at ALTC and the definition that I'm using for learning technologists or educational technologists seems to veer away a little bit from the ALT definition, which I would suggest actually kind of brings learning design into the equation far more than in the Australian experience. Educational technologists are largely there to facilitate educational technologies, so implementing, evaluating, procuring, working with vendors, all of that kind of stuff, making sure that academics and other people know how to use it appropriately. So, there is definitely a need for pedagogical knowledge, but it is largely seen as a technological role. ETs will also be involved in building learning activities and resources, putting things up into the learning management system, making multimedia assets, videos.

There is a tech support component. Even ed techs kind of get a little bit resentful about only being seen as the tech guy, but I think that that is actually a fairly common complaint among all EdAdvisors. And there is also a capability building component to the education technology role.

Finally, we've got learning designers. More likely to be women, definitely more likely to hold professional positions. As the name suggests, definitely involved in designing, teaching and learning. Probably more to do with designing learning activities, learning resources than curriculum. Definitely there to build capability, build learning and teaching resources.

And they do have or claim a role in facilitating education technology as well. This is probably because the learning designer role is much more of an all-rounder kind of role than either the AD or the ed tech kind of roles. Which means that sometimes they can feel that they're a little bit shut

out of things at the very pedagogical end of the spectrum or the very technological end of the spectrum.

And so, they're kind of the middle child of the EdAdvisor family.

Let's have another song. [Music plays] Welcome back. That was the Vividels, covering the classic Go-Betweens track Was there anything I could do?

Now I previously mentioned that my or the Australian view of Educational/Learning technologist varies a little from the UK definition which is probably important given that we are actually here at ALTC. The clarity of third space roles is widely regarded as one of our biggest challenges, both in terms of consistency of titles and also the role definitions. But why does this matter?

I think there are actually four major implications for having poorly defined and poorly understood roles. It means that it is harder for academics to find the right help, the help that they actually need, and if they find it, it makes it harder to trust the expertise of the person that they're working with. If they don't understand what the person is capable of or what their responsibilities are, then why should they trust them? Poorly defined roles also make it harder to hire good people. If I'm looking at, you know, LinkedIn or a job ad site or whatever, and I type in a particular search term, and for whatever reason the University of Warwick has listed someone as a technology specialist, LMS, I'm not going to find that role. Finally, leaders may not know how to appropriately use people working in these EdAdvisor third space roles.

Now these issues with clarity over, you know, role titles and role definitions are nothing new in my review of literature. I found an article from 1972 by Geis and Klaassen, where they were basically discussing whether educational technologists or instructional designer should be the term that is being used. And they did a review of all of the titles being used in their institutions. So yeah. This is, this is not a particularly new issue. I worked on a paper with some colleagues Kate Mitchell and Chie Adachi in 2017, where we looked at 37 job ads and we found 27 distinct titles for basically these three EdAdvisor roles that I've been exploring.

So, is this a solvable problem? Probably not. But I think it's definitely still worth exploring. And one of the things, one of the themes that's really emerged in the research that I've done is that the ambiguity is not always a bad thing. A lot of people noted that it creates a little bit more flexibility. There's a little bit more fluidity. You've got opportunities to do activities that might not necessarily be associated with your role because people don't always necessarily know what you should be doing. So yeah, there's, there's a balance that needs to be found. So, I think that's an interesting finding.

Let's have another song. [Music plays] Johnny Cash there from American Three with his take on Tom Petty's "I won't back down". I like this song because it embodies the main quality I have had to draw on as I've progressed through my PhD. Spite.

Now one factor, which has had a massive impact on the ability of third space practitioners to enable better learning and teaching is the divide between academic and professional staff in higher education. In my own research, my survey sample was 77% professional staff and 23% academic staff. The first thing worth noting is that when I asked survey respondents what factors they felt served as barriers to their work, 69% of the professional staff, but only 35% of academic staff, selected the academic professional divide, and that was statistically significant.

There were a few other statistics of note. I asked a series of questions about the extent to which people felt that their work was understood and valued by different stakeholders, academics, leaders, and people in other EdAdvisor roles. For the question about whether academics value their work, 71% of with a professional classification broadly agreed, but 57% of people with an academic classification broadly agreed. Also statistically significant. There are a couple of major themes that emerged from the interviews. One, which is probably no major surprise, is that there is a social status hierarchy between academic and professional staff and that having an academic role means that there is a sense of shared understanding with academics, which often makes life a little bit easier. Interestingly, the academic professional question was largely not seen as a barrier to relationships between people in EdAdvisor roles. We're all quite capable of happily getting along.

Let's have another track. [Music plays] Sharon Jones and the Dap Kings there with a song you may recognise from the soundtrack to The Big Lebowski. "Just dropped in (to see what condition my condition was in)". That was originally performed by Kenny Rogers and the First Edition, you're listening to ALTC Radio. I'm Colin Simpson playing covers and banging on about my doctoral research into third space professionals in Australian higher education.

One aspect of higher education, which plays an important part in the efficacy of EdAdvisors, or third space practitioners is the relationship between central areas of the university and the faculties or disciplinary areas, if you want to call them that. This plays an important part. In shaping the ability of these third space practitioners slash EdAdvisors to support better learning and teaching. In my sample, 62% of respondents worked in a central division. 29% reported working in a faculty unit, and 9% selected other. Now, there was no significant difference in the questions that I asked about if people feel that their work is understood or valued by different stakeholders, depending on whether they were central or faculty based, and there was no significant difference on the questions about their ability to contribute to decision-making on educational practices or educational technologies.

However, there are a lot of big feelings, generally speaking. About the relationship between central and faculties. Probably the key theme was that there were competing priorities and a power imbalance. The faculty people had a local focus. It was discipline based, and it was very much about learning and teaching, whereas people in the central area were perceived as being more focused on the big picture and having a whole of institution focus. And this is, you know, within responses from the interviewees as well as the common themes within the literature. And so these relationships can be quite fraught because there's a sense that central people will barge into faculty areas to try and impose one size fits all solutions and they're not interested in local initiatives.

And on both sides, there was basically a sense that there's a lack of understanding either of local needs or big picture needs. So there's definitely some challenges for us to work out in the relationships between central and faculty.

Let's have another song coming to the end of the show here on ALTC Radio. [Music plays] That was a version of a Robert Palmer song, Johnny and Mary by Norwegian DJ Todd Terje featuring Brian Ferry on vocals.

In between songs I've been discussing some of the factors which affect the work of third space practitioners in higher education. One final factor that has not received a lot of attention in the literature is the impact of organisational structures on EdAdvisors.

This includes whether units are centralised or decentralised, so there might be a single central unit, and members of that unit are embedded in faculty teams, or it might simply be all faculty teams with no central unit. Organisational restructures and instability was another big part of this theme. New structures can mean that you are working alongside new people or no longer working with your old colleagues.

New leaders inevitably bring new plans and projects, which can mean that something that you've worked on for months or years is simply abandoned. And of course, there's the very real risk of job losses, none of which is conducive to getting things done. Working with other stakeholders in the institution was also often regarded as a challenge, particularly when working with university IT departments to whom educational technologies are often just a small part of their overall portfolio

Time now for one more song, and this one is an original. [Music plays] And that one was "Everything is now" by a Melbourne artist, Jess Ribeiro. Thought I would slip an original track in among the covers to symbolise the original contribution that this research is meant to bring to the field. Something along those lines. This brings us to the end of my show here on ALTC Radio.

I'd like to thank Dom Pate for indulging me. I hope you've enjoyed the tunes and found my work of some interest. If you are a third space practitioner or have an interest in this area, I'd like to encourage you to consider getting involved in an event that I'm organising later in the year. The Third Space Symposium. This is an event in two parts. We're going to have a one day in person event on Sunday, the 1st of December. Now that will be at the University of Melbourne in Australia, so maybe that's a little bit of a stretch, but preceding that we are having a two week online asynchronous, "slowposium". Where we will be exploring all facets of third space experience, work challenges, and opportunities.

So you can find out some more information about that at thirdspacesymposium.com. That's all one word. And if you'd like to know more about my research on the third space or the TELedvisors Network or anything really, please look for me on socials. I'm Colin Simpson on LinkedIn and gamerlearner in other places.

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